

NEWSLETTER 1 June 2019

This is the first newsletter of the IS-ENES3 H2020 Research Infrastructure project.

Entering in its third phase in January 2019, IS-ENES3 is the Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling (ENES). It supports the development and exploitation of climate models, in particular the European contribution to the WCRP international experiments CMIP and CORDEX. It fosters collaboration between twenty-two European institutions and is led by CNRS for IPSL.

This newsletter will be quarterly delivered. Do not hesitate to share this newsletter with anyone who would like to subscribe!

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Upcoming Events

Workshop 'Defining a cutting-edge future for sea ice modelling'

The IS-ENES3 workshop "Defining a cutting-edge future for sea ice modelling", organized by CNRS, Met Office and DOE, in conjunction with the NEMO Sea Ice Working Group and the CICE Consortium, will take place from the 24th to 26th of September 2019 in Laugarvatn, Iceland. Workshop invitation will be restricted to the sea ice modelling community, as numbers are limited by room availability. However, it may be possible to join the workshop by sending a message describing your experience and the reason why you would like to attend to the organisers: ed.blockley@metoffice.gov.uk and martin.vancoppenolle@locean-ipsl.upmc.fr.

[Read more](#)

Climate4Impact Coding Sprint!

An IS-ENES3 technical meeting will take place from June 18th to 21st, 2019 (WP10/JRA3), devoted to the development of the Climate4Impact portal. It will be preceded by a DARE/IS-ENES3 collaborative meeting on June 17th. It will be hosted at KNMI, De Bilt, Netherlands. The main objectives of these two complementary meetings are to enable partners, involved in the development of the ENES Climate Data Infrastructure and especially on climate4impact, to work together on specific items, with high collaboration and dedicated full time. It will consist of brainstorming sessions, followed by coding and developments in

focused groups on identified specific points in the brainstorming sessions, and a summary of achievements.

[Read more](#)

Past Events

IS-ENES3 Kick-off meeting!

The kick-off meeting of IS-ENES3 took place on January 9-11, 2019 at Sorbonne Université in Paris.

The kick-off meeting gathered more than 80 participants from 11 European countries

[Find the presentations](#)

3 teams selected after the 1st call for applicants to the OASIS Dedicated User Support !

On December 2018, IS-ENES3 launched its first **transnational call** for applicants to access the OASIS Dedicated User Support. Included in the work package 6 "Services on European ESMs and Software Tool", this action provides technical help at user site to design, upgrade or enhance the implementation of the OASIS3-MCT coupler interface in climate model(s) and/or to set up a tailored and computationally efficient coupled system. This year, a total of 3 person-months of Dedicated User Support is offered to the 3 different groups that were selected at ETH Zurich, MetOffice and GEOMAR. Provided by CERFACS, this service is available to any European climate research laboratory responding to the selection call.

The next call will be opened on September 2019.

IS-ENES@EGU2019

The General Assembly of EGU (7-12 April 2019) in Vienna provided an opportunity to present some features of IS-ENES3 to a broad European audience. Besides taking parts in discussions and attending sessions, IS-ENES3 teams specifically participated in three sessions offering the following contributions:

Introduction to the Climate4Impact portal

IS-ENES3 offered a short training on how to use the Climate4Impact portal to access, visualize and process climate data. This session targeted impact researchers and other people with only basic knowledge of climate data.

[See more](#)

Climate4impact: Enhance usage of research data and support researchers with climate analysis

In session:
Earth/Environmental Science Applications on Cloud and HPC Infrastructures

[See more](#)

IS-ENES impacts on the path towards the infrastructure sustainability

In session:
Monitoring, assessing and increasing the impact of environmental and the Earth system Research Infrastructures

[See more](#)

Events related to IS-ENES3

IS-ENES3 at the HPCKP

The work done these past months on ESMValTool and GPUs' optimization will be presented by Saskia Loosveldt from Barcelona Supercomputing Center in the next explained in the HPC Knowledge Meeting '19 (HPCKP) on the 14th of June 2019, from 10:45 to 11:15am.

[See more](#)

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